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A STUDY ON THE ADJUSTMENT AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS

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Abstract

The present study aimed to investigate the adjustment of the student of adolescence period in West Tripura in relation to their academic achievement, age, gender etc. in a sample of 120 adolescents (60 boys & 60 girls). Data was analyzed by using Standard Deviation, Mean, Percentile, t-test, Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The result of the study indicated that there were no significant differences between boys and girls in adjustment and academic achievement in adolescence period. The result also revealed that there was a significant difference among emotional adjustment, social adjustment, educational adjustment and academic achievement in adolescent period. The researcher also found that there exist positive relationship between adjustment & academic achievement of boys& girls in adolescence period of West Tripura District. The study has implications for students of adolescence period, teacher, parents and policy makers as well.

Keywords: Adjustment; Academic Achievement; Adolescent.

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1. Introduction

Adjustment can be interpreted as both process and the outcome of that process in the form of some attainment or achievement what the individual can attain in terms of success in his ambition or pride. The concept of adjustment was first given by Darwin, who used it as an adaptation to survive in physical world. Achievement is nothing but the result of one's adjustment. Academic achievement is the outcome of education, the extent to which a student has achieved his educational goals. Academic achievement is commonly measured examination

and continuous assessment. Academic achievement can be defined as excellence in all academic discipline in class as well as extracurricular activities. Academic achievement is the knowledge or skill developed in school subjects usually designed by the test scores or marks assigned by the teacher. There are so many conditions that contribute to high academic achievement one of them is adjustment. When we look back on our teenage years and recall the uncertainties the conflicts and sometimes the loneliness it is easy to recognize that adolescence is a time when we move from childhood to adulthood, mentally, emotionally, socially and Physically – Adolescence is the most important period of human life. According the view of G. Stanley. Hall, an American psychologist, Adolescence is the period of storm and stress'. His book Adolescence (1904) helps mark the age period a focus of scientific study. Hall saw adolescence party as an upheaval a disruption of peaceful growth. Accordingly to Anna Freud, a prominent theorist and daughter of Sigmund Freud adolescence represented no period of crisis or stress, but was instead an orderly developing of a set of slowly maturing interests and activities.

An individual need emotional adjustment, social adjustment as well as educational adjustment also. Good adjustment helps him to overcome from different difficulties. It helps to make good relationship with the society, with peer group. It will make the good relation with school and himself or herself also. Adjustment is a continuous demand a changes in the environment is inevitable with every situation or environment adolescents have to adjust to make good social relationship to improve academic achievement, to avoid emotional misbalance. **Gates & Jersild (1948)** Adjustment is a continuous process in which a person varies his behaviour to produce a more harmonious relationship between himself & his environment. Adjustment of a student is related to arriving at a balanced state between his needs and satisfaction. Need of individual are multidimensional. Good adjustment is realistic and satisfying. Students have good adjustment in all aspect of their life if there is balance between their academic-intellectual, emotional, social and other needs and their satisfaction. Individual-excellence is possible on one hand by inculcating, cultivating and developing scientific attitude and a spirit of enquiry in the minds of the young and on the other hand by promoting creativity and innovative even in them to deal with any challenging demands.

Adjustment as an achievement means how the effectiveness with which an individual can function in changed circumstances and is as such related to his adequacy and regarded as an achievement that is accomplished either badly or well (Lazarus, 1976). Adjustment, although a universal phenomenon can be studied through its various aspects or dimension like health, adjustment, home-adjustment and school or professional adjustment. It measure, the degree to which one may be describe as adjusted. Every moment of one's life one has to do this or that. To be able to do it one must know the right or wrong and bad of things and actions. In this regard his social obligations and responsibilities he has to develop sound philosophy of life.

2. Rationale of the Study

Educational adjustment is the capacity of a person to respond to the educational environment it in clefs curricular and co-corrector activates. The major part of adolescent life is spent in the school one of the important function of schooling is to help the pupils to develop those capabilities that may help them to make effective adjustment in life. A well-adjusted person has very few things to complain about. Poor school adjustment leads to low academic achievement,

behavioural problems and even school dropout. Unless the problems of adjustment are diagnosed it is impossible to undertake remedial measures. The onset of adolescents varies from culture to culture, depending on the socio economic condition of the society. So proper guidance is needed for adequate adjustment in school, home and society. The sound mental health is one of the first requisite conditions of development. Adolescence is marked with a number of problems which affect the mental health. The study of adolescence is very important in order to preserve, cure and prevent incidences of male adjustment.

Tripura is a tiny state known as one of the sister of North-East. But in this hilly state the people of different race and culture are living together. To live with different culture, to live with the different race of people, adjustment is needed. It is a recognized fact that in every culture of the world, it is possible to learn certain skill and behaviour at some stages, which make the adjustment in society more adequate. The speedy industrialization and westernization of society is creating a number of problems. The adolescents of 21st century are facing different types of problems but beside this they are adjusting themselves with the changing society. So it is needed to find out whether there is a significant relation between the adjustment and educational achievement.

3. Objective of the Study

The objectives of study as follows:

- To study the adjustment of the student of adolescent period in west Tripura district.
- To estimate the academic achievement of adolescent students in common subjects.
- To compare the adjustment of boys and girls students of adolescence period.
- To compare the academic achievement of boys and girls students of adolescence period.
- To compare the emotional adjustment and academic achievement in adolescence period.
- To compare the social adjustment and academic achievement in adolescence period.
- To compare the educational adjustment and academic achievement in adolescence period.
- To estimate the relationship between adjustment and academic achievement of boys in adolescence period.
- To estimate the relationship between adjustment and academic achievement of girls in adolescence period.

4. Hypotheses of the Study

Following hypotheses were proposed to test the objectives:

H₁. There is a significant difference between the adjustment of boys and girls students of adolescence period.

H₂. There is a significant difference between the academic achievement of boys and girls students of adolescence period.

H₃ There is a significant difference between the emotional adjustment and academic achievement in adolescence period.

H₄. There is a significant difference between the social adjustment and academic achievement in adolescence period.

H₅. There is a significant difference between the educational adjustment and academic achievement in adolescence period.

H₆. There is a significant relationship between the adjustment and academic achievement of boys' student of adolescence period in West Tripura.

H₇. There is a significant relationship between adjustment and academic achievement of girls' student of adolescence period in West Tripura.

5. Method of the Study

The investigator employed descriptive survey method of research for the present study as it was concerned with the present aims of determining the status of the phenomenon under investigation. A sample of 120 students of class IX was taken randomly from six schools of west Tripura districts. Out of them, 60 students were boys and 60 students were girls.

6. Tools Used

The following tool was used for the conduct of present investigation

- 1) Adjustment inventory for school students by Dr. A.K.P Sinha and R.P Singh was used as a tool for measuring extent of adjustment these tools measures three areas of adjustment viz. social, emotional and educational adjustment.
- 2) The total marks of common subjects obtained in the previous year (class viii) were taken as criterion of academic achievement.

7. Result and Interpretation of the Data

For the present study, the researcher had used a variety of statistical technique like Standard Deviation, Mean, Percentile, t-test, Pearson product moment correlation. The researcher arranged the data that were obtained from the students.

Figure 1: Bar graph represents the percentage of boys & girls student in total adjustment.

Interpretation: from figure 1 it can be interpret that the Girls were 'Excellent' and 'Good' than Boys in terms of total adjustment. But Girls were lagging behind Boys in 'Average', 'Unsatisfactory' and 'Very Unsatisfactory' in total adjustment, which means that in the case of total adjustment Girls were better than the Boys.

Figure 2: Bar graph represents the percentage of boys & girls student in emotional adjustment.

Interpretation: Figure2 interprets that the mixed result found in emotional adjustment. Girls were “Excellent” & “Good” than the Boys. But maximum numbers of Boys were “Average”, “Unsatisfactory”& “Very Unsatisfactory” in emotional adjustment. So, it reveals that the emotional adjustment of Girls were better than the Boys.

Figure 3: Bar graph represents the percentage of boys & girls student in social adjustment.

Interpretation: Figure3 indicates that in social adjustment Boys were more “Excellent” than Girls and maximum number of Girls were “Good” & 0% in “Very Unsatisfactory”.

Figure 4: Bar graph represents the percentage of boys & girls student in educational adjustment.

Interpretation: From figure 4 it can be found that maximum number of Boys were better in educational adjustment than the Girls. But it is also found that less number of Girls were ‘Unsatisfactory’ and ‘Very Unsatisfactory’ in educational adjustment.

Figure 5: Bar graph represents the percentage of boys & girls of their academic achievement.

Interpretation: Figure 5 indicates that there were maximum numbers of Boy’s “Average Achiever”. The Boys were better in “High Achiever” than the Girls but Boys & Girls were equally “Lower Achiever” in academic achievement. So it revealed that Boys score better than Girls in their Academic Achievement.

Table 1: The significant difference between the mean adjustment of boys and girls students of adolescence period.

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	't' Value	Level of significance
Boys	60	15.41	7.15	118	1.37	0.05
Girls	60	13.78	5.85			Not significant

Interpretation: The result of the analysis from Table 1 revealed that the obtain 't' value 1.37 was lower than the calculated value(1.98) which was statistically not significant at 0.05 level. So the hypothesis was rejected. The result indicates that there were no significant differences between the adjustment of Boys and Girls students of adolescence period. But the mean score of the Boys were higher than the Girls. So it implies that the adjustment capacity of Boys were better than the Girls

Table 2: The Significant difference between the means of academic achievement of boys and girls students of adolescence period.

Group	N	Mean	SD	D	df	't' Value	Level of significance
Boys	60	243.66	78.49	18.79	118	1.26	0.05
Girls	60	224.84	84.41				Not significant

Interpretation: The Result in Table 2 indicates that the calculated 't' value 1.26 was lower than the tabulated value(1.98) at 0.05 level of significance. So the hypothesis was rejected. Thus the result shows that there were no significant differences between the academic achievement of Boys and Girls student of adolescence period. However, the mean score of Boys was higher than the Girls. So it implies that the Boys academic achievement were better than the Girls.

Table 3: The Significant difference between the emotional adjustment and academic achievement in adolescence periods.

Group	N	Mean	SD	D	df	't' Value	Level of significance
Emotional Adjustment	120	4.79	1.99	229.3	238	30.75	0.05
Academic Achievement	120	234.27	81.71				Significant

Interpretation: The Result in Table 3 indicates that the obtain 't' value was 30.75 which was higher than the tabulated one(1.97) which was statistically significant at 0.05 level in 228 degree of freedom. So the hypothesis was accepted. Hence the result revealed that there were a significant difference between the emotional adjustment and academic achievement in adolescence period.

Table 4: The Significant difference between the social adjustment and academic achievement in adolescence period.

Group	N	Mean	SD	D	df	't' Value	Level of significance
Social Adjustment	120	4.79	1.99	229.48	238	30.76	0.05

Academic Achievement	120	234.27	81.71				Significant
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Interpretation: The Result of the analysis from Table 4 revealed that the calculated ‘t’ value was 30.76 was higher than the tabulated value (1.97) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the alternative hypothesis was accepted and it was concluding that there were significant difference between the social adjustment and academic achievements of adolescence period.

Table 5: The Significant difference between the Means of educational adjustment and academic achievement of adolescence period.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	D	df	‘t’ Value	Level of significance
Educational Adjustment	120	4.79	1.92	229.51	238	30.77	0.05 Significant
Academic Achievement	120	234.27	81.71				

Interpretation: The Result of the analysis from Table 5 showed that the calculated value was (30.77) higher than the tabulated value (1.97) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore hypothesis was accepted which implies that there were significant difference between the educational adjustment and academic achievements of adolescence period.

Table 6: Co- efficient of correlation of the scores of adjustment and academic achievement of boy’s student in adolescence period.

Variable	N	Co- efficient of correlation	df	Level of Significance 0.01	Remark
Adjustment	60	.02	58	Not significant	Negligible
Academic Achievement					

Interpretation: The result of the analysis from Table 6 showed that the calculated ‘r’ value being +0.02 which was not significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level in 58 degree of freedom. So the hypothesis was rejected. But there was a positive relation between adjustment and academic achievement of Boys though it was negligible.

Table 7: Co- efficient of correlation of the scores of adjustment and academic achievement of girl’s student in adolescence period.

Variable	N	Co- efficient of correlation	df	Level of Significance 0.01	Remark
Adjustment	60	0.28	58	significant	Low Co-relation
Academic Achievement					

Interpretation: The result of the analysis from Table 7 showed that the calculated value ‘r’ being +0.28 which was significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level in 58 degree of freedom. Therefore, this hypothesis was accepted. It was also observed that there were a positive relationship between

adjustment and academic achievement of Girl but it is low in co- relation. So it can be observed that there were a significant correlation between adjustment and academic achievement in the case of Girls in adolescence period.

8. Discussion

From the result we get two important points that girls and boys are not significantly differ in adjustment and academic achievement. Generally we think that the adjustment of boys and girls are different. There are lots of thinks which influence the adjustment of the adolescence like environment, situation, age, proper care etc. In the case of academic achievement also we can see that there is a no significant difference between the academic achievement of boys and girls. Ganai M.Y.Dr.Mir Ashraf Muhammad, (2013) found that male & female groups do not differ significantly on educational adjustment and two group do not differ significantly on academic adjustment. Traditionally we, think that a well-adjusted student can do good academic performance. Our statistical analysis also tells that there is a positive co-relation between the adjustment and academic achievement of boys and girls. But girls have more co-relation with adjustment and academic achievement than the boys. Adjustment of a student is related to arriving at a balanced state between his needs and satisfaction. Adolescence is the period during which human personality developed new dimensions. It's the period of sudden unfoldment of new social instincts. But high expectation from parents, the community and the society contributes to emotional disturbance. Failure to achieve the desired success at school heighten emotionality; sometimes leading to running from homes and even committing suicide. Fear of failure may serve as the motivator to the adolescent to work hard for the examination. At this stage social changes are reflected in the influence of the peer group, new values in friendships selection and new values in social expectation. T.P.Joseph (1969) claims that an adolescent wants as a friend 'someone to be trusted, someone to talk to, someone who is dependable.'

The secondary and the senior secondary school must be transformed into an 'activity school' because activity has an irresistible appeal for every normal child and its natural path to the goal of the knowledge and culture. We can't escape from social relationships in real life. A school should provide situations in which the adolescent may be gradually led to understand the relationships in community, country, and in the world at large. It is absolutely essential that every secondary and senior school should have a comprehensive programme of guidance, especially educational and vocational.

9. Conclusion

Life presents a continuous chain of struggle for adjustment. Adjustments are the outcome of the individual's attempt to deals with stress and meet with needs: also, his efforts to maintain harmonious relationships with the environment. According to smith, H.C. 'A good adjustment is one which is both realistic and satisfying. At list in a long run, it reduces to a minimum the frustrations, the tensions and anxieties which a person must endure'. From the finding, research work lead the researcher to conclude that there are no observe significant differences between the boys and the girls in adjustment and academic achievement also. From the data it can be show that the emotional, social and educational adjustment, rising the levels of adjustment problems of boys and girls. But there was a co-relation between the adjustment and academic achievement of

boys and girls also. So if the students of adolescence period adjust in good way, then there is a possibility to do good academic performance. But if they have any adjustment problem then counselling and continuous assistance is necessary, which will play a vital role in providing adequate coping skill with the situation. Students should be given an opportunity to express their ideas and discuss their problems with school authorities. It develops self-confidence and mental satisfaction among the students. Play hobbies, excursions, discussions etc. provide excellent opportunities to explore and express their feelings. These should be organised for developing good mental health of students and their healthy adjustment. Parents and teachers should provide intellectual, social and emotional support to children at the time of stress and tension. In this way students will be enabling to recognise their strong and weak characteristics to avoid unnecessary aspirations.

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